

Health, Law, and Dignity: A Human Rights Analysis of Healthcare access for LGBTQ+ Persons and Sex Workers in India

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This article critically examines the healthcare barriers faced by LGBTQ+ and sex workers in India. It is observed that there exists a significant gap between constitutionally guaranteed rights and their implementations. Several weakness of the Article 14, 15, and 21 are discussed along with major Supreme court cases that have contributed in the changes in laws. The healthcare barriers include the laws which criminalize parts of sex work and rules that discriminate against transgender people. Also a great detail on how different marginal and vulnerable communities such as LGBTQ+, people with disabilities, transgender and minor sex groups that belong to more than one vulnerable communities suffer to access equal rights. It also highlights community-led projects like the Sonagachi Project, Kerala's queer-inclusive healthcare, and Ashodaya Samithi as examples that have contributed to make lives of these vulnerable communities easier by empowering them. Finally the article suggests wide-ranging changes to end criminal penalties for consensual adult sex work, allowing gender recognition through self-declaration, making medical education LGBTQ+ inclusive, creating strong complaint system etc. The article argues that these marginalized groups are equally eligible to fair healthcare system and this is not an extra or optional issue, but a core part of India's promise of dignity and justice for all.

Keywords: LGBTQ+ healthcare access, sex workers' rights, health equity, intersectional discrimination

Healthcare access as a Fundamental Right for Marginalized Communities in India

The right to health is fundamental to enjoy every other rights to human. The WHO has provided a definition which is inclusive in nature. It points to a state of complete psychophysical and social well-being, and not just the absence of disease (UJA, 2024). This takes into account the social factors that also contribute to shape an individual's life. Somehow this important right is not mentioned in Indian constitution but is established through courts as part and parcel of the Rights to Life and Personal Liberty enshrined in Article 21 (Viswanath, 2023; Khandekar et al., 2012). For marginalized communities such as LGBTQ+ and sex workers this right to health has been a challenging journey. This research paper focuses on an important social problem related to these marginal communities. They have a gap in their mentioned rights vs what they are actually getting in reality. There are laws that harm their work (Immoral Traffic Prevention Act) or laws that are not properly implemented (Transgender Persons Act, 2019). The healthcare system does not serve this community either. Then there is a deep social stigma even at places that are supposed to assist these communities to live a healthy lives (Chakrapani et al., 2023; Pandya & Redcay, 2020). The

supreme court of India mentioned that the "right of life" is not just staying alive similar to animals but to live with a dignity. Every individual has a right to live with respect and dignity irrespective of their identity and work. Unfortunately the society doesn't treat the marginal communities like sex workers and LGBTQ+ with same dignity. They are humiliated and verbally abused almost everywhere so that hinders their attempt to getting healthcare services like the rest of the population. The Navtej Singh Johar death with LGBTQ+ rights and similarly Budhadev Karmaskar care dealt with rights of sex workers. In both cases the violation of their constitutional rights was observed through the suppression of their healthcare seeking behavior (Wintemute, 2019; De, 2013).

To show the depth of this social problem the current research is designed to first paint the picture of health rights in India, then challenges of LGBTQ+ and sex workers, then how belonging to more than one group ends up compounding the disadvantage for such individuals. This will also highlight the activities by society serving these communities and filling the gaps left by government failures. Along with this comprehensive list the study will suggest practical solutions as well.

The Constitutional and Legal Bedrock of Health Rights in India

India has robust laws that protect health rights on its citizens but there is a mismatch in the implications. The Article 21 is the backbone and starting point of health law. It was earlier limited to the right of "life and personal liberty" which now includes "life" means not just being alive but living with dignity owing to amendments brought by Supreme court. The new changes include right to psychophysical health, access to healthcare services and facilities, clean air, water, and workplace (Gandhi, 2024; Khandekar et al., 2012).

Furthermore Articles 14 and 15 ensures the right to be treated

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fairly and with dignity. As per Article 14, anyone facing discrimination due to any law may challenge the policy (Venkatchalam et al., 2020). And Article 15 ensures citizens that they cannot be discriminated on the basis of caste, religion, sex, race, or place of birth. The broadening of term of "sex" now includes LGBTQ+ individuals also (Dixit, 2019; Wintermute, 2019).

Judicial Expansion of Health Rights: Key Supreme Court Interpretations

There is a gap in written law that guarantees the health of right, to tackle this the courts have created changes to protect these rights, unintentionally creating challenges for the then government to actually deliver. Some example of cases that assisted the building of health rights are as following:

Pramanad katara v. Union of India (1989): This case established that every emergency patient should get treatment without formalities of paper work especially when the injuries are life threatening.

Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samity v. State of West Bengal (1996): As per this one the government has a constitutional duty to build and maintain public health sector to serve anyone in need and the denial to health services in government hospital is a violation of Article 21 (Yadav et al., 2021).

Bandhua Mukti Morcha v. Union of India (1997): As outcome of this case lead to the declaration that health is part of our right to life which is guaranteed by the constitution (Giordana, 1986).

Consumer Education and Research Centre v. Union of India (1995). This provides workers the right of health during service and after retirement and combines Article 21 with government guidelines (DPSPs).

Ram Lubhaya Bagga v. State of Punjab (1998). The outcome lead to the confirmation that the protection of public health is an important government duty under Article 21 and Article 47 (Saikia, 2019).

National Health Legislation

India protects health with the help of multiple laws covering separate areas. The older Indian Medical Council was replaced with the National Medical Commission Act of 2019 due to corruption problems. This law regulates how the doctors are trained and should behave professionally but this does not include teaching LGBTQ+ health issues or how to serve sex workers. Unfortunately this leads doctors remain ignorant and discriminate against these communities (Agarwal & Thiyam, 2023).

Healthcare and LGBTQ + Rights in India

The status of LGBTQ+ community has changed from criminal to having protection by the constitution but the healthcare services are still not fully in their reach.

Legal Milestones: Decriminalization to the Transgender Persons Act

Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India (2018) made the same sex relation legal and struck down Section 377 of Indian Penal Code (Wintermute, 2019; Dixit, 2019). The supreme court mentioned that this old law violated Article 14, 15, 19, and 21. Justice Chandrachud gave explanation that the old law would erase identities and increase the cases of HIV and sexually transmitted diseases by making healthcare services out of reach from LGBTQ+ people. The court also quoted Mental Healthcare Act of 2017 as per which the

discrimination based on sexual orientation is prohibited and being gay is not a mental illness (Khan, 2025).

The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act, 2019 makes it mandatory for government to provide gender affirmative care and remove the discrimination in healthcare system. However there is a major flaw in this. The transgender individuals are mandated to get an identity recognition certificate from District Magistrate which contradicts the earlier ruling that stated that people should be able to self-identify without any approval from government (Chakrapani et al., 2023; Gupta, 2022).

Barriers to LGBTQ+ Healthcare access

The laws for LGBTQ+ community have significantly improved over time but lack of knowledge and system failure is still an obstacle for them getting medical care.

Stigma and Discrimination: There have been instances reported by LGBTQ+ individuals of being verbally/physically abused, treated refusal and even sexual abuse (Arora et al., 2022; Pandya & Redcay, 2020). Especially those who visibly look like people belonging to the queer community are more vulnerable to such harsh discrimination (Griffin et al., 2023). A 2024 UNDP survey found that the fear of being judged and bias from medical staff actually reduces the likelihood of LGBTQ+ community individuals from reaching hospitals for medical care until some emergency is not there to be immediately attended (Vora et al., 2023).

Inadequate Professional Training and Systematic Gaps: The entire healthcare system is built on the assumption of everyone being a cisgender; the forms have only male and female options, lack of gender-neutral bathrooms in hospitals, the chosen families are not recognized for giving medical consent, the medical insurance does not include LGBTQ+ specific needs, and same sex couple are not recognized legally which stops them from taking medical decisions for their partner or inherent property (Agarwal & Thiyam, 2023).

LGBTQ+ Health Disparities

There are questionable practices in healthcare systems that discriminate against LGBTQ+ communities in India.

Mental Health: Belonging to this community brings a whole package of difficulties for mental health. There is constant stress of being a minority, their families reject or disown them, and the frequent violence from the society. In India, 52% gay men reported mental disorders, over 12% faced severe depression and one-third of transgender teenager have attempted suicide in past year (Wandrekar & Nigudkar, 2020). Three out of four LGBTQ+ people hide their identity due to fear of being rejected, facing loneliness, shame and PTSD.

HIV/STIs: The prevalence of HIV are dangerously high among transgender people (3.1%) compared to general population (0.26%). This number is even worse among individuals who cannot read or write (8.4%) and individuals involved in sex work (9.4%). Another concerning factor is that one in three gay men and one in four transgender individuals who are infected with HIV are not aware of this disease.

Gender-Affirming Caer Barriers: There are not enough trained doctors to serve transgender people due to which these individuals end up in dangerous and unregulated clinics since affording healthcare services in private hospital is out of reach for them. Another factor contributing to this problem is that transgender individuals are required to go through psychological evaluation to prove that they are transgender before getting a treatment (Chakrapani et al., 2023). Even recently during COVID-19 the

transgenders faced higher job losses and they could not get vaccines since their ID documents did not match their actual gender (Gaur et al., 2023).

Research Gaps: Researchers conducting study on this community have ignored lesbian and bisexual women, transmasculine people, intersex people, and those living in rural areas. In this population a longitudinal study is desperately required.

Sex Workers' Rights and Healthcare access in India

The government run public healthcare system provides sex workers free condoms to prevent HIV, but the police treats it as an evidence of sex work, creating a confusing situation for sex workers.

The Legal Dilemma: The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act (ITPA)

This law creates a legal trap. It does not make sex work itself legal but everyone around it ultimately becomes a criminal, making it impossible for sex workers to conduct their profession. Section 3 prohibits brothel keeping, even two sex workers cannot stay together in a place for safety as they will get arrested for running a brothel. Section 4 criminalizes living off sex work earning, due to which the dependent immediate family members can also be arrested. And then Section 8 permits police to arrest sex workers even if they are trying to get clients.

Sex workers avoid going to clinics due to fear of being arrested. Police sometimes “rescue” them forcefully and then detains them in lock up instead of providing any actual help. Then after this rescue the sex workers are made to go through mandatory health checkup and the reports are often disclosed publicly, all of this in turn scares these sex workers from getting tested in the future (Lawyers Collective, 2006).

Judicial Recognition of Rights: Budhadev Karmaskar

Budhadev Karmaskar v. State of West Bengal (2011) declared sex workers are full citizens and all legal protections and rights to live with dignity under Article 21 shall be provided to them. The court ordered the government to establish healthcare, education, and committees to prevent trafficking. These committees also helped sex workers with leaving sex work and ensured a dignified condition for those who wishes to continue this work (Garg, 2023).

Healthcare access Barriers

The ITPA allows police to harass sex workers which forces them to hide and avoid health clinics (All India Network of Sex Worker, 2023). The medical staff degrades them by asking such questions, breaking the confidentiality which again contributes to less health care visits by this community. Many sex workers are not even aware of health services, then many clinics have inconvenient hours, location is far from reach, or lack of such facilities in rural areas (Tripathi & Singh, 2024).

Many targeted programs have significantly increased the use of condom among sex workers to 91% and have reduced the new incidences of HIV rates to 1.6% by 2017 (Chachra, 2019). But this is not consistent across all states such as Maharashtra (6%) and Karnataka (6%). Then the use of condom is not consistent especially with non-paying partners and clients who force sex workers (Shewale & Sahay, 2022).

Majority of the programs focus on only HIV prevention and ignore reproductive needs. This profession often faces unwanted pregnancies which leads to dangerous illegal abortions. In Goa 26% of sex workers reported having at least one abortion. Their options for birth control are limited to condom only (Tripathi & Singh, 2024).

The violence faced by this community by clients, partners, pimps and police is another important area to consider. In Chennai only 98% sex workers reported severe abuse from intimate partners and 76% faces abuse from clients (Panchanadeswaran et al., 2010). This violence often causes HIV and chronic pain as they are forced into unprotected sex (Sarkar, 2022).

The number of sex workers facing mental health difficulties is high. Between 38.3% to 73% suffer from depression due to stigma and financial stress (Iaisuklang & Ali, 2017). And depression in turn is found associated with risky sexual behaviors, creating a dangerous cycle (Jana et al., 2017).

Intersectional Vulnerabilities: Compounded Healthcare Challenges

The Indian legal system is designed to treat each type of discrimination separately so the individuals who belong to more than one marginalized groups end up facing combined bias and multiplied difficulties.

Transgender Sex Workers: This community faces triple stigma- their gender identity, occupation and non-conformity “normal” gender expectations- which heightens the HIV risk as the constant stress doesn't let them negotiate the use of condom with clients. The violence they experience from romantic partners, clients and members of gharana systems (transgender community networks) is often disturbingly high (Ganju & Saggurti, 2017). Since they have two identities of sex workers and transgender, both community rights organization fails to provide assistance to this group.

LGBTQ+ Individuals from Lower Castes/Economic Strata/Rural Areas: Similar to above mentioned two roles double difficulties is observed in this group. They face discrimination from healthcare providers due to their caste and due to their LGBTQ+ identity (Jadhav & Taneja, 2021). The evidence comes from southern India where Dalit transgender and intersex people reported higher rates of physical and sexual abuse by medical professionals (Nikarthil & Kejriwal, 2021). The Scheduled Caste and Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act, 1989 is not inclusive of this combined caste and gender identity (Baradar, 2024). Financial limitations does not allow them to go for private gender-affirming care (Lopes, 2022). The LGBTQ+ people end up facing stricter social rules, high rejection from families, and almost no medical staff who understands their unique needs in rural areas (Shaikh, 2025).

Minor Female Sex Workers: The Most Vulnerable

India has POCSO ACT 2012 and Juvenile Justice Act 2015 but they are not properly enforced. As an outcome the young girls who are forced into sex work are the most vulnerable groups; they are trapped due to poverty and lack of education (Yadav, 2024). They fear authority and know little about safe sex, meaning almost no healthcare access and very high rates of STI rates.

LGBTQ+ Persons with Disabilities: Sexual orientation and disability both create double problems for this group (Sarkar, 2022). There is no intersection between disability rights systems and transgender rights system. The consensus of disability only

recognizes “male” or “female”, ignoring non-binary people. This group also faces triple problems; first they are not accessible buildings for disabled, then doctors may wrongly treat gender identity as a disability symptoms, and disability-related expenses (Lopes, 2022). Both the disability and LGBTQ+ rights movements are separate and often fail to represent those who belong to both of these communities.

Civil Society and Community-Led Initiatives

Since government is not effective in providing health care services to these communities the community members have taken initiatives to become their primary healthcare advocates.

Government Programs

The National AIDS Control Programme (NACP) which is run through NACO-funded interventions and implemented by NGOs has reached a great success in reducing HIV rates and increasing the use of condom use among high risk groups (Prinja et al., 2011). However, this only focuses on HIV and ignores reproductive care, sexual and mental health needs (Kale et al., 2025). The program fails to adequately address specific needs of transgenders and ignores adolescents in sex work (Yadav & Alam, 2024).

NGO Interventions

The Humsafar Trust is India's first community-based HIV treatment clinical, providing mental health and legal support. They also have challenged Section 377 (Humsafar Trust, 2025). Another such organization is Naz foundation which won the 2009 Section 377 legal case and now runs a residential care for HIV/AIDS infected adolescents and home-based family support system (The Better India, 2025).

Sex Worker Organisations

Prajwala provides shelter to trafficking survivors and SANGRAM works on building trust among sex workers to access healthcare (Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, n.d.; Tripathi & Singh, 2024).

Effective Community-based Models

Multiple projects have contributed effectively towards goals of HIV prevention and supporting the LGBTQ+ community. The Sonagachi Project (Kerala) has successfully transformed HIV prevention into a health and human rights, providing peer education, safety advocacy and providing a middle ground with police and ultimately reducing HIV rates and high condom use (Basu et al., 2024). Kerala's Queer-Inclusive Public Healthcare is a collaborative effort of the state government and Mariwala Health Initiative which makes LGBTQ+ a part of mainstream healthcare system. In this the required training is provided to hospital staff and transgender community members are employed to connect sex workers with medical service providers (YourStory, 2025). Ashodaya Samithi (Chennai) is a sex worker collective effort which along with HIV prevention focuses on overall reproductive health such as cervical cancer screening and providing community based delivery system in healthcare (Lazarus et al., 2021).

Pathways to Equitable Healthcare: Recommendations

There is a need for law, healthcare and community to work to work

together for fair health outcomes among LGBTQ+ people.

Legal and Policy Frameworks

Countries require national laws to ban discrimination based on sexual orientation, gender identity, and sex work with real enforcement.

- The laws associated with sex workers require amendments to decriminalize consensual adult sex work.
- Transgenders should allow recognition by self-declaration, without requiring surgical conditions and clear penalties for violations against them.
- Legal recognition for LGBTQ+ relationships so that their partners can make medical decisions and be next of kin.

Health System Reforms

- Medical staff should include evidence based gender-affirming care guidelines such as WPATH-style protocols.
- The sensitization towards such communities should be regular and mandatory.
- The testing should be confidential for HIV/STI and affirm mental health support.
- More investment in public hospitals to provide affordable gender-affirming surgeries and hormones.
- Easy to use complaint systems to assist them in seeking improvements.

Conclusion: Toward Health Equity for All

Indian Constitutions promises equality with dignity to everyone but LGBTQ+ people and sex workers constantly face discrimination from law, healthcare, and society. They are treated as criminals because of their identity and profession. It is not a matter of only insufficient funding but a human rights crisis by the law which punishes them and the doctors who are not trained properly to deal with these communities. The government systems support the current prejudice against these communities. There are both sides in action; in one place the government is providing them services, and on the other hand the law is stopping these communities from accessing those services. The laws need to catch up with the promises made by the constitution of India. The progress would mean treating these communities as full citizens with rights who are not perceived as helpless and “high-risk” groups. There have been successful examples like Sonagachi Project and Kerala inclusive healthcare system that show true fairness comes only when laws protects instead of punish. A fair society is judged by how it treats its most marginalized people. Providing dignified healthcare to all vulnerable groups is not options but it is an essential to India's constitutional promise.

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